

Frustule: the silica bioscaffold from oceans

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Abstract: The global demand for smaller and smaller structures in electronic, optical, chemical, and biomedical devices combined with the need to reduce the requirements for high temperatures and aggressive chemicals to manipulate materials, pushed the studies to find new suitable biomaterials. Biomimetic engineering is the global trend to try to obtain materials with complex architecture and unique properties from natural organisms; in this case, we shall focus on what nature has optimized as a hard, elastic, and highly complex material derived from diatom outer silica shell, called frustule. Diatom frustules in the last 30 years were largely used as nanostructured materials for several applications, due to their hierarchical layers of porous membranes, providing high surface area, and structural architecture for ion transport. Furthermore, the cheap cultivation of diatoms (it only requires CO₂, water, salts, and light), not competing with crops for the arable land, could be considered as a promising and economic source of this biomaterial. Although the potential of frustules as biomaterials and their possible application has been already well understood, it is necessary to study which bioscaffold has the best physical-chemical properties to be exploited for future functionalization concurrently with the highest productivity. Moreover, to obtain biosilica from diatoms it is crucial to totally remove the organic matter adhered on their surface, preserving frustule shape, and avoiding its erosion. Three ways are mainly used to obtain frustules: (i) oxidative washing protocols using H₂O₂ solutions, the most commonly used, (ii) chemical treatments with acids and (iii) baking frustules at high temperatures, the simplest and least expensive method more aggressive and altering frustule architecture. The aim of this project was thus to investigate three species of diatoms, *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Conticribra weissflogii* and *Navicula sp.*, distinct in size and geometry, and assess their productivity for a future scale-up in frustule production; concurrently, in a world moving towards sustainability and looking for always more eco-compatible processes, our purpose was to assess which cleaning procedure has less impact on our planet, comparing through Life Cycle Assessment two procedures, one based on oxidative washing and the other on chemical treatment with acids. What emerged was that, despite the higher growth rate of the smallest species *C. muelleri* as compared to the other species, the biomass produced by *C. weissflogii* and *Navicula sp.* was strongly higher and more suitable for a future industrial scale-up; moreover, it was observed that frustules of the small *C. muelleri* was not resistant to calcination process. The assessment of the carbon footprint highlighted that Friedrichs method using acids is the most sustainable option with an estimated environmental burden of 4kg of equivalent CO₂ compared to 20 kg resulting from the oxidation method; acidic cleaning procedure allows to save electricity, use more sustainable reagents, and produce less wastewater to obtain 150 mg of cleaned frustules.

Biography of presenting author: AP is a marine biologist, and she focused her research interest on the biology of diatoms, an extraordinary group of unicellular photosynthetic organisms that are very abundant in phytoplankton. In particular, during PhD, she studied their silica cell wall called frustule in terms of morphological and functional evolution; the adaptive functions she addressed were defence against predation and buoyancy. Now she is working on the response of diatoms to climate change. Concurrently, she has started to investigate frustules as potential supports for chemical catalysis being involved in the EU project DESIRED.

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